

Continuous Usage Intention in Online Food Delivery (OFD) During Covid-19: Case Study in Banda ACEH

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Abstract: This study analyzes the effect of using Online Food Delivery (OFD) in terms of design, namely design aesthetic appeal and design aesthetic formality on Continuous usage intention involving PAD theory (pleasure, arousal, and dominance) as a mediation during the COVID-19 period. Questionnaires were given to OFD users in Banda Aceh City, Indonesia, and managed to obtain 180 questionnaires. Based on SEM analysis, aesthetic formality affects the continuous usage intention but the aesthetic appeal does not. The result reveals that the use of design aesthetic appeal does not affect continuous usage intention, the use of design aesthetic formality affects continuous usage intention, the use of design aesthetic appeal affects pleasure, the use of design aesthetic appeal does not affect arousal, the use of design aesthetic appeal affects dominance, the use of design aesthetic formality affects pleasure, the use of design aesthetic formality does not affect arousal, the use of design aesthetic formality affects the dominance, pleasure does not affect the continuous usage intention, arousal does not affect continuous usage intention, dominance affects continuous usage intention, pleasure does not mediate the use of design aesthetic appeal on continuous usage intention, arousal does not mediate the use of design aesthetic appeal on continuous usage intention, dominance mediates design aesthetic appeal to continuous usage intention, pleasure does not mediate design aesthetic formality on continuous usage intention, arousal does not mediate design aesthetic formality on continuous usage intention, and dominance mediates design aesthetic formality on continuous usage intention. In these results, it concludes that only dominance functions as mediation in the model, and the mediation role is full mediation for the role of design aesthetic appeal on continuous usage intention, and partial on the role of design aesthetic formality on continuous usage intention.

Keywords: Online Food Delivery, Pleasure-Arousal-Dominance, Continuous usage intention

I. Introduction

Massive growth in the field of online services with smartphones has brought changes in people's lifestyles in general (Sjahroeddin, 2018). One of the applications provided is Online Food Delivery (OFD). OFD is an application for ordering and delivering food from various restaurants via websites or apps. Customers usually search for food restaurants and choose from several available items then enter their delivery address and wait for the food to be delivered to their destination (Pigatto, Machado, Negreti, & Machado, 2017). This greatly facilitates the lives of people who cannot buy directly, especially during the global pandemic caused by the coronavirus (COVID-19) in 2019 (Pan et al., 2020). Research by (Rita, Oliveira, & Farisa, 2019) wrote that OFD is also part of e-services which is defined as the ability of internet sites both in the form of applications and the web that are used to provide services both in the form of shopping, purchasing, ordering and distribution effectively and efficiently with the online platform.

Research by (Kumar & Shah, 2021) wrote that OFD can make it easier for users and food vendors to fulfill their daily needs only through smartphones. Of course, with the benefits offered by the application, users feel that the application is very helpful for them in terms of ordering food so that they have the intention to reuse the application (continuous usage intention), especially in this COVID-19 era which requires social distancing (maintaining social distancing). App users who want certain products will also be affected by their purchase decisions when this pandemic occurs (Adam, Mahdani, Indris, & Putra, 2022).

Continuous usage intentions/interest in the use of sustainability refers to customers making purchases or using a product in an application on an ongoing basis (Indira, Dewi, & Utami, 2019). According to research (Kumar, Jain, & Hsieh, 2021) Intention of sustainable use, in general, is a person's loyalty to a particular product, both goods, and services. According to research by (Han, Wu, Wang, & Hong, 2018), continuous usage intention refers to every individual who

repurchases a certain product/service for the same business. (Loureiro, Stylos, & Bellou, 2021) wrote that users will carry out continuous usage intentions in an application if they feel happy (pleasure), passionate (arousal) when using the application and have the ability to freely use the application without any encouragement from anything (dominance) from the application.

Based on the research of (Kumar & Shah, 2021), the Pleasure, Arousal, and Dominance (PAD) theory were proposed by Mehrabain Russel to find out that a person's emotions towards the use of technology can be influenced by PAD itself. (Kumar et al., 2021) studied various factors into continuous usage intentions, the context of a pleasant application experience, and some emotional experiences that can encourage customers to continue using the application, one of which is the visual and ease of use of the application known as application design. That study shows that aesthetic application design in terms of attractiveness and formality (aesthetic appeal and aesthetic formality) plays an important role in determining continuous usage intentions for an application, and application design (aesthetic design & design formality) plays an important role in continuity/comfort when using applications that lead consumers to continuous usage intentions.

A bad design will make users unwilling to use the application because it is difficult to operate the application. A font size that is too small can make it difficult for users to read information, on the other hand, too large a size of font will make customers uncomfortable. An appropriate font size accompanied by other elements such as choosing a good shop/food display (image) can attract users, appropriate icon buttons, fonts (easy to read), and selection of appropriate application colors are also able to make users perform continuous usage intentions. The selection of attractive colors can help and become the most important point for users in carrying out continuous usage intentions of an application. An application that is easy to use is also one of the important points that users consider. Applications that do not confuse customers with the form, visuals, and directions of an application can make it easier for users and easier to use the application so that it will make users carry out continuous usage intentions towards an application.

In the province of Aceh itself, the most widely used OFD is in the city of Banda Aceh, Indonesia. Currently, there are three OFD in Banda Aceh, namely GrabFood, GoFood, and MaximFood. The use of OFD is also very helpful for people in Banda Aceh City, especially during social distancing during the COVID-19 pandemic. This is evidenced by conducting an initial survey on 31 respondents who use a food delivery application in Banda Aceh City.

However, the use of this application can be viewed from the use of design which is also very limited, especially in Banda Aceh, for that reason it is necessary to do further research on the use of OFD based on application design because from several studies the results of consumers reusing the application are determined by the sense of design, namely the feeling experienced when using the application, of course, using the emotional basis as a mediation, namely pleasure, passion, and dominance. Application design must have an appeal that makes consumers reuse the application (Assaker & Hallak, 2013). Therefore, the author conducted research related to continuous usage intentions in OFD During the Covid-19: A Study in the City of Banda Aceh.

II. Literature

Continuous usage intention in OFD

(Han et al., 2018) explained that Continuous usage intention in OFD is a decision made by the user/application users who will always use the OFD in the future. According to (H. M. Lee & Chen, 2014) the interest to continue/reuse a product or service is the most important thing to achieve success for the company. When users return to using the application, it will be able to create high loyalty and will make it easier for companies to carry out promotions and also get good profits in the future. It is very important for companies to carry out continuous usage intention because, in the digital market, which is increasingly changing their behavior and acquiring new users, it is very costly rather than to get old users to make purchases/use sustainability services (Kumar & Shah, 2021). The indicators used to measure Continuous usage intention in this study are (1) Will use in the future, (2) Will use often in the future (3) Will continue to use in the future.

Pleasure

(Yang, Kim, & Zimmerman, 2020) Pleasure is defined as how satisfied, or how happy consumers are with a product. (Hall, Elliott, & Meng, 2017) also explain that pleasure is the extent to which each individual feels satisfied and happy with their environment. Pleasure refers to the degree to which the individual feels good, full of joy, feeling happy about the situation.

Pleasure is measured by an assessment of verbal reactions to the environment (happy as opposed to sad, pleasant as opposed to unpleasant, satisfied as opposed to dissatisfied, hopeful as opposed to hopeless, and relaxed as opposed to bored) (Semuel, 2005). In this study, pleasure will be measured by several indicators, namely (1) Happy (2) Comfortable (3) Satisfied.

Arousal

(Chang, Chih, Liou, & Hwang, 2014) arousal is defined to see the extent to which consumers feel stimulated or excited. Research by (Miniero, Rurale, & Addis, 2014) explains that arousal is an individual feeling that leads to attraction and stimulation. (Loureiro et al., 2021) wrote that arousal refers to the level of arousal or the level of excitement, alertness, and activity caused by OFD. Arousal is a symptom that indicates an increase in physiological and psychological activity in a person. It can be explained that arousal is a level of excitement. There is the lowest level of arousal and the highest level of arousal that a person can experience.

Arousal refers to the degree to which a person feels alert, excited, or in an active situation. Arousal is considered as a respondent's report, such as when it is stimulated, opposed, or relaxed (Semuel, 2005). Arousal in this study refers to the extent to which consumers feel passionate, enthusiastic, and cheerful in using food delivery applications, so in measuring arousal in this study several indicators from previous studies will be used. The indicators used in this study to measure arousal are (1) Passionate (2) Enthusiastic (3) Cheerful.

Dominance

In the research of (Hall et al., 2017) Dominance is a cognitive state that reflects freedom, autonomy, or control for consumers. Dominance is a state of individuals whom they believe that they can control the circumstances in their environment (Miniero et al., 2014). More specifically, dominance refers to consumers feeling in control, strong, or having difficulty using applications (Bradley & Lang, 1994); (Mehrabian & Russell, 1974) If they feel dominant then consumers feel they can control, have power, and have no trouble.

Dominance refers to the level of influence and power in specific OFD, realization, and outcome (Loureiro et al., 2021). In this study, dominance will focus on being able to control the use and feel able to control the application. The indicators to measure dominance in this study are (1) Can be controlled by using OFD, (2) Can Control using OFD, (3) Ordering through the application becomes dominant.

Aesthetic Appeal of the Design (AP)

Aesthetic appeal refers to the level of pleasure and enjoyment felt by consumers obtained from online interface experiences (Chang et al., 2014). Aesthetic appeal can create the emotional pleasure that comes from how much the user experience feels the pleasure or pleasure experienced by consumers in using OFD (Chang et al., 2014). (Lee & Jeong, 2012) wrote that aesthetic appeal serves to give a positive impression to site visitors when they use or explore a website or application. There are 3 indicators used to measure aesthetic appeal in this study, namely; (1) Interesting (2) Creative (3) Impressive.

Aesthetic Formality of the Design (AF)

Aesthetic Formality is an online interface design that reflects simplicity and good structure and increases user responsiveness with easy-to-read (fonts) (Chang et al., 2014). (Reppa, McDougall, Sonderegger, & Schmidt, 2021) also write that, Aesthetic Formality refers to the extent to which the OFD design is well organized or simple and also has a customer-friendly layout, this needs to be considered to create a good and easy experience in navigating an OFD.

(Harris & Goode, 2010) explain that layout and functionality are interrelated variables. Layout refers to the visual arrangement of the website that can attract the attention of consumers, while functionality refers to the ease that consumers feel as site visitors to the layout arrangement. In this study, there are 3 indicators used to measure aesthetic formality (1) Organized (2) Organized (3) Easy to understand.

III. Method

Research Location and Object

This research is a kind of quantitative research. The survey was conducted in Banda Aceh. The data and information used in this study were obtained from the distribution of online questionnaires. Questionnaires were given to people in Banda Aceh who use an OFD application. Furthermore, the object will be associated with six variables which include Aesthetic appeal, Aesthetic formality, Pleasure, Arousal, Dominance, and Continuous Usage Intention.

Data Analysis Tools

In this study, the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the AMOS was used, which is a statistical tool for hypothesis testing. The Sobel test was used to complete the significance of the indirect effect test. The following is a path diagram (path analysis) contained in this study and its hypotheses.

Figure 1. Structural Model

- H1 : design aesthetic appeal affects continuous usage intention,
- H2 : design aesthetic formality affects continuous usage intention,
- H3 : design aesthetic appeal affects pleasure,
- H4 : design aesthetic appeal affects arousal,
- H5 : design aesthetic appeal affects dominance,
- H6 : design aesthetic formality affects pleasure,
- H7 : design aesthetic formality affects arousal,
- H8 : design aesthetic formality affects the dominance,
- H9 : pleasure affects the continuous usage intention,
- H10 : arousal affects continuous usage intention,
- H11 : dominance affects continuous usage intention,
- H12 : pleasure mediates the design aesthetic appeal role in continuous usage intention,
- H13 : arousal mediates the design aesthetic appeal role in continuous usage intention,
- H14 : dominance mediates the design aesthetic appeal role in continuous usage intention,
- H15 : pleasure mediates the design aesthetic formality role in continuous usage intention,
- H16 : arousal mediates the design aesthetic formality role in continuous usage intention
- H17 : dominance mediates the design aesthetic formality role in continuous usage intention.

IV. Result

Table 1. Regression Weight

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
CUI	<---	AP	0.135	0.132	1.022	0.307
CUI	<---	AF	0.274	0.125	2.188	0.029
PLS	<---	AP	0.394	0.175	2.252	0.024
ARO	<---	AP	0.011	0.029	0.383	0.701
DOM	<---	AP	0.608	0.139	4.374	***
PLS	<---	AF	0.326	0.140	2.334	0.020
ARO	<---	AF	0.072	0.047	1.510	0.131
DOM	<---	AF	0.390	0.119	3.265	0.001
CUI	<---	PLS	0.011	0.095	0.115	0.909
CUI	<---	ARO	0.701	0.612	1.144	0.252
CUI	<---	DOM	0.269	0.100	2.694	0.007

The role of design aesthetic appeal in continuous usage intention of OFD in Banda Aceh (H1)

Based on the results obtained, the P value of H1 is 0.307, so it is greater than 0.05. Therefore, this H1 rejects Ha and accepts H0, meaning that the use of OFD's design aesthetic appeal in Banda Aceh has no significant effect on continuous usage intention because it does not match the predetermined criteria above.

The role of design aesthetic formality in continuous usage intention of OFD in Banda Aceh (H2)

The result shows H2 test provides a CR value of 2.188 with a standardized coefficient of 0.274. So, it explains that if the use of design aesthetic formality increases by 1%, it will increase continuous usage intention by 27.4%. Kumar & Shah (2021) explain that design aesthetic formality as a form or condition that makes it easy for users when use the application, is generated from user ratings in using the application, if the user finds it easy to navigate the application, then the application is good.

The role of design aesthetic appeal in pleasure of OFD in Banda Aceh (H3)

The result shows H3 test provides the P value is 0.024 so it is smaller than 0.05, it concludes that H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted. This means that the use of design aesthetic appeal has a positive and significant effect on pleasure. Based on the results of data processing, obtained a CR value of 2.252 with a standardized coefficient of 0.294. So, it can be said that if the use of design aesthetic appeal increases by 1%, it will increase pleasure by 29.4%.

The role of design aesthetic appeal in arousal of OFD in Banda Aceh (H4)

The result shows H4 test provides the P value is 0.701 so it is greater than 0.05, it concludes that H0 is accepted and Ha is rejected. So there is no role in using design aesthetic appeal in affecting arousal in OFD in Banda Aceh

The role of design aesthetic appeal in dominance of OFD in Banda Aceh (H5)

The result shows H5 test provides a P value that is smaller than 0.05. This reveals that the H4 test rejects H0 and accepts Ha because the results show Then the CR value is 4.374 with a coefficient of 0.608. If the use of design aesthetic appeal is increased by 1%, it will increase dominance by 60.8%.

The role of design aesthetic formality in pleasure of OFD in Banda Aceh (H6)

The result shows H6 test provides a P value of 0.020 which is smaller than 0.05, so it figures that H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted. Then the CR value is 2.334 and the coefficient is 0.326 where if the design aesthetic formality increases by 1% it will increase the pleasure of the OFD by 32.6%.

The role of design aesthetic formality in arousal of OFD in Banda Aceh (H7)

The result shows H7 test provides a P value was 0.131 is greater than 0.05, which explains to accept H0 and reject Ha. This shows that the design aesthetic formality has no significant effect on arousal.

The role of design aesthetic formality in the dominance of OFD in Banda Aceh (H8)

The result shows H8 test provides a P value smaller than 0.05, so it concludes to reject H0 and accept Ha. Also obtained a CR value of 3.265 and a coefficient of 0.390, meaning that if the design aesthetic formality increases by 1%, it will increase dominance by 39%.

The role of pleasure in continuous usage intention of OFD in Banda Aceh (H9)

The result shows H9 test provides a P value of 0,909 greater than 0.05, so it reveals to accept H0 and reject Ha. This means there is an insignificant effect of pleasure on continuous usage intention in OFD.

The role of arousal in continuous usage intention of OFD in Banda Aceh (H10)

The result shows H10 test provides a P value is 0.7252 is greater than 0.05, so it explains to accept H0 and reject Ha. So there is no role of arousal in affecting continuous usage intention.

The role of dominance in continuous usage intention of OFD in Banda Aceh (H11)

The result shows H11 test provides a P value of 0.007 is smaller than 0.05, so it leads to reject H0 and accept Ha. It also obtained a CR value of 2.694 and a coefficient of 0.269, meaning that if dominance increases by 1%, it will increase continuous usage intention by 26.9%.

The role of design aesthetic appeal and design aesthetic formality in continuous usage intention through pleasure, arousal, and dominance of OFD in Banda Aceh (H12 - H17)

Indirect effect testing was done by using the theory of Barron and Kenny through SEM-AMOS. The result provides the direct effect of aesthetic appeal on continuous usage intention is 0.135, the indirect effect of aesthetic appeal on continuous usage intention through pleasure is 0.063, through arousal is 0.050, and through dominance is 0.279. Furthermore, the direct effect of aesthetic formality on continuous usage intention is 0.274, the indirect effect of aesthetic formality on continuous usage intention through pleasure is 0.056, through arousal is 0.066, and through dominance is 0.283. So, it reveals that aesthetic appeal and aesthetic formality generally have a more direct influence on continuous usage intention than its indirect effect through the mediation of pleasure, and arousal. Only the indirect effect of aesthetic appeal and aesthetic formality through dominance is greater than the direct effect. And for comparison, Sobel Test was used to test all the indirect hypothesis (H12 until H17), and can be revealed as follows.

Table 2. Indirect Effect of AP - DOM - CIU (H14)

Input:		Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a	0.608	Sobel test: 2.29137097	0.07137736	0.02194197
b	0.269	Aroian test: 2.24912052	0.0727182	0.02450483
s _a	0.139	Goodman test: 2.33609558	0.07001083	0.01948626
s _b	0.100	Reset all	Calculate	

Table 3. Indirect Effect of AF - DOM - CIU (H17)

Input:		Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a	0.390	Sobel test: 2.07927975	0.05045497	0.03759165
b	0.269	Aroian test: 2.02375377	0.05183931	0.04299549
s _a	0.119	Goodman test: 2.13964219	0.04903156	0.03238369
s _b	0.100	Reset all	Calculate	

Based on the results of the Sobel test, only 2 indirect hypotheses have been shown to have a significant effect ($P < 0.05$, as shown in Table 2 and 3), namely the effect of design aesthetic appeal on continuous usage intention through dominance (H14), and the effect of aesthetic formality on continuous usage intention through dominance (H17), while H12, H13, H15, and H16 showed the results of the Sobel test with P value > 0.05 . In these results, it can be seen that only dominance functions as mediation in the model, and the mediation role is full mediation for the role of design aesthetic appeal on continuous usage intention, and partial on the role of design aesthetic formality on continuous usage intention.

V. Conclusion

This study concludes that the use of design aesthetic appeal does not affect continuous usage intention, the use of design aesthetic formality affects continuous usage intention, the use of design aesthetic appeal affects pleasure, the use of design aesthetic appeal does not affect arousal, the use of design aesthetic appeal affects dominance, the use of design aesthetic formality affects pleasure, the use of design aesthetic formality does not affect arousal, the use of design aesthetic formality affects the dominance, pleasure does not affect the continuous usage intention, arousal does not affect continuous usage intention, dominance affects continuous usage intention, pleasure does not mediate the use of design aesthetic appeal on continuous usage intention, arousal does not mediate the use of design aesthetic appeal on continuous usage intention, dominance mediates design aesthetic appeal to continuous usage intention, pleasure does not mediate design aesthetic formality on continuous usage intention, arousal does not mediate design aesthetic formality on continuous usage intention, and dominance mediates design aesthetic formality on continuous usage intention. In these results, it can be seen that only dominance functions as mediation in the model, and the mediation role is full mediation for the role of design aesthetic appeal on continuous usage intention, and partial on the role of design aesthetic formality on continuous usage intention.

These findings mean that the model of increasing continuous usage intention in OFD in Banda Aceh City is a function of increasing suitability of design aesthetic appeal and design aesthetic formality, as well as increasing dominance. This tested model can be the basis for the development of further test models, by adding other variables such as discount variables, coupons, and other benefits provided by OFD, and expanding the scope. Some of the findings in this research can also be the basis for recommendations to practitioners, especially research subjects, namely OFD developers for Banda Aceh City. The application makers should focus more on the function of the application and also

not necessarily leave the aesthetic aspect of the application alone. A good application is that it can meet the needs of its users in an easy, simple, and organized way for users in the city of Banda Aceh in particular.

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